

[Date of publication xxxx 00, 0000, date of current version xxxx 00, 0000.]

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.0429000

An Augmented Reality System with an Offline LSTM-Based Fault Recognition Model for Sewer Pipeline Inspection

EVGENY V. VOTYAKOV¹, ANDREAS ANDREOU¹, FOTIS LIAROKAPIS¹,

¹CYENS Centre of Excellence & University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus (e-mail: e.votyakov@cyens.org.cy)

Corresponding author: Fotis Liarokapis (e-mail: f.liarokapis@cyens.org.cy)

ABSTRACT Detection and assessment of sewer pipeline faults are critical for maintaining urban infrastructure. This paper presents a real-time augmented reality (AR) mobile application for visualizing sewer pipelines. The application is deployed on a tablet device that meets the minimal hardware requirements: a rear camera for AR functionality, along with integrated GPS and inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensors for spatial localization and orientation. The system also incorporates an offline machine learning model for recognizing and annotating pipeline faults. This model combines handcrafted features with a long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network. The handcrafted features include Gabor filters (GF), local binary patterns (LBP), histograms of oriented gradients (HOG), and gray-level co-occurrence matrices (GLCM). Both the type of handcrafted feature and the LSTM sequence length were varied in experiments using three industrial CCTV datasets, which were annotated by professionals to indicate frames with and without faults. Performance metrics across different model variants were compared, and the LBP-LSTM model was found to achieve the best results.

INDEX TERMS Augmented reality, sewer pipeline faults, machine learning, handcrafted features, LSTM.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE combination of Augmented Reality (AR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), offer new solutions in the pipeline industry by improving the speed and accuracy of inspections. Sewer pipelines are typically concerned with maintenance, inspection, training, and safety. Efficient detection and assessment of sewer pipeline faults is critical to maintaining urban infrastructure. Traditional methods for inspecting underground sewer systems are based on manual assessments and closed circuit television (CCTV) video-based inspections to identify structural issues. These methods are labor-intensive, costly, and time-consuming, by highlighting the potential of unsupervised and semi-supervised learning methods to reduce the reliance on manual inspection while improving detection accuracy.

Previously, Kumar et al. applied AR to inspect pipelines in a water-treatment facility by combining a 3D point cloud with LiDAR scans and camera footage, superimposing virtual pipe models onto the actual surroundings [1]. Similarly, Zhao et al. enabled inspectors to visualize an AR representation of subterranean pipes, where pressure and flow irregularities were highlighted and notifications were generated for likely leak areas based on the system's hydraulic model [2].

Recent advances in intelligent infrastructure inspection demonstrate how digital twins and physics-aware neural models can enhance fault diagnosis and maintenance decision-making. For example, Wang et al. introduced a digital-twin-based elevator fault diagnosis framework combining PINNs and e-RGCN, showing how hybrid physical-data-driven models enable more reliable fault prediction in real-world industrial systems [3]. Such approaches highlight a broader trend toward persistent, interpretable digital twin ecosystems for infrastructure management—an ultimate direction toward which AR-enabled field systems, such as ours, can evolve.

In machine-learning-based defect detection, lightweight convolutional models have recently demonstrated strong performance for infrastructure inspection tasks. Li et al. proposed an optimized YOLOv8-based crack-detection network incorporating SE-V2 modules, offering a compact yet high-accuracy baseline for real-time inspection in pipeline systems [4]. Their work reinforces the importance of efficient architectures capable of running on constrained hardware—one of the motivating factors behind our use of handcrafted texture descriptors combined with an LSTM model in the present feasibility study.

In sewer defect classification specifically, Hu et al. introduced TMFF, a trustworthy multi-focus fusion network capable of multi-label recognition in sewer inspection videos [5]. Their work demonstrates the feasibility of multi-label defect categorization (e.g., cracks, roots, deformation), which is essential for detailed maintenance workflows. In contrast, the present study focuses on a binary fault/no-fault pipeline due to constraints in dataset size, heterogeneity, and limited positive samples. The objective at this stage is to assess whether an offline ML model can be reliably integrated with an AR visualization tool—a feasibility step before adopting multi-label pipelines.

Furthermore, recent work emphasizes the integration of physical knowledge into AI models for sewer inspection. Di et al. developed a theory-guided neural network for intelligent siltation diagnosis in drainage pipelines, demonstrating how domain-informed architectures improve accuracy and robustness compared to purely data-driven methods [6]. Similarly, Wang et al. proposed physically interpretable wavelet-guided networks for industrial fault prediction, underscoring the increasing importance of interpretability in safety-critical diagnostics [7]. Our choice to combine handcrafted features with temporal modeling aligns with this emphasis on transparency, offering interpretable texture-based cues that can be traced back to the original CCTV imagery.

AR has been also applied in enhancing pipeline maintenance processes by minimizing uncertainty and mistakes in excavation by enabling workers to see buried pipelines and assets on-site through a tablet or headset [8]. Another study developed a remote AR assistance system that improved the technician's spatial understanding of instructions provided by a remote expert [9].

Moreover, Cote and Mercier proposed an augmentation method that overlays 2D pipe maps on the road surface and aligns them with matching elements in the real world through a pre-captured 3D mesh [10]. Li et al. developed a mobile AR system for urban gas pipeline networks that supports operations and maintenance by enabling quick identification of abnormal conditions (e.g., pressure drops on specific pipes) while looking directly at the physical site [11].

The ultimate goal of this research is to enhance the situational awareness and improve decision-making efficiency of maintenance workers during inspections and repairs. This paper presents a mobile AR application for intelligently visualizing detected faults and pipe structures directly in the field. An offline machine learning method is proposed for recognizing faults. Results from the machine learning model combined with AR for assisting inspectors to view the pipeline structure and assess pipe characteristics on-site.

Motivation. Despite extensive research in automated fault recognition, current CNN-based approaches are often computationally expensive and unsuitable for field deployment on low-power inspection devices or tablets. Moreover, maintenance workers still lack an intuitive method to translate video-detected faults into real-world excavation locations, resulting in unnecessary digging, higher cost, and safety risks.

This gap between offline fault recognition and on-site spatial understanding motivates our work.

Contributions. This study provides three main contributions: (1) A lightweight, fully offline feature–LSTM model that combines handcrafted texture descriptors (LBP, Gabor, HOG, GLCM) with temporal modeling for fault recognition in sewer CCTV footage. (2) A complete evaluation across three industrial datasets, including systematic variation of feature types and LSTM sequence lengths. (3) A mobile augmented reality application that maps detected faults into geospatial coordinates and visualizes them on-site using Unity3D, enabling accurate, low-cost, and real-time field assessment.

II. IMAGE RECOGNITION AND FAULT DETECTION

This section initially presents machine learning (ML) approaches to image recognition. Next, algorithms designed to detect anomalies in the CCTV footage are presented. Finally, elements of both approaches are combined, integrating image recognition techniques with fault detection methods. Part of the scientific background motivating this section has been integrated into the Introduction for better contextualization, as suggested by the reviewer.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have demonstrated effectiveness in classifying faults from image data. Yokoyama and Matsumoto (2017) [12] developed a machine learning-based system for detecting concrete cracks automatically, demonstrating early integration of traditional ML approaches in structural monitoring. Gopalakrishnan et al. (2017) [13] proposed a deep convolutional neural network with transfer learning to detect pavement distress, highlighting the advantages of data-driven models in computer vision applications. Dung (2019) [14] implemented a fully convolutional neural network (FCN) for concrete crack detection, achieving pixel-level accuracy without manual feature extraction. Li et al. (2020) [15] introduced a deep CNN model for classifying pavement cracks, showing promising results in automated crack identification and categorization. Kumar and Ghosh (2020) [16] proposed a dual-channel deep convolutional neural network for detecting concrete cracks. The model combines spatial and contextual features from two separate channels to improve detection accuracy, particularly in challenging conditions like noise, shadows, and varying textures. The approach demonstrates enhanced performance over traditional single-channel CNNs. Xu et al. (2021) [17] tackled the challenge of detecting extremely thin cracks by introducing a specialized deep learning approach that enhances sensitivity to fine structural details. Their method combines high-resolution feature extraction with optimized training strategies to push the limits of precision in thin crack detection, outperforming conventional models in delicate crack scenarios. Patra et al. (2021) [18] designed PotSpot, a participatory sensing system that uses deep learning to detect potholes via crowdsourced mobile data, merging IoT concepts with AI. Xu et al. (2022) [19] compared Faster R-CNN and Mask R-CNN for crack detection, providing insights

into the performance of region-based deep learning models in structural health monitoring. Li et al. (2023) [20] utilized UAV imagery combined with Faster R-CNN for automated bridge crack detection, showcasing the integration of aerial sensing and deep learning for infrastructure inspection.

Significant progress has been made in video anomaly detection (VAD) during the past few years. Mishra et al [21] surveye a progress in the field. The CNN-VAD method is exemplified by Tutar et al. (2024) [22] who proposed a hybrid approach combining the TensorFlow build-in ResNet-50 and long-short term memory (LSTM) model for video anomaly detection. This approach leverages the strengths of both architectures, capturing complex spatial and temporal patterns in video data. However, ResNet-50, with its 50 layers, might be computationally expensive and challenging to implement in resource-constrained environments, such as robotic systems. Moreover, the CNNs may suffer from overfitting due to their high complexity, but the handcrafted features offer a controlled approach, reducing the risk of overfitting and improving the generalizability of the model, particularly in environments with limited training data [23]. In such cases, lightweight CNN models could offer a more efficient alternative, requiring less computational power and memory while maintaining relatively good accuracy. In this work, we use a lightweight CNN and demonstrate it is highly effective on identifying faults in a sewer pipeline.

Unsupervised machine learning methods, such as fault detection algorithms, offer a promising alternative by detecting unusual patterns without the need for labeled data. Fang et al. (2020) [24] applied fault detection algorithms to video sequences without the need for an annotated fault sample database. The Sewer-ML dataset and benchmark provides a comprehensive resource for evaluating automated sewer fault classification models [25]. Unfortunately, the dataset links [25] were invalid at the moment of this work.

In this paper, we combine handcrafted feature extraction, such as texture analysis methods such as: Local Binary Patterns (LBP) [26], Gabor filters [27], Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG [28], and Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) [29] with temporal correlation models like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. Handcrafted features capture spatial correlations in the data, providing computationally efficient and informative descriptors for texture patterns. LSTM networks, on the other hand, excel at modeling temporal dependencies in sequential data, making them suitable for analyzing video sequences where temporal dynamics are crucial.

Combining these approaches allows for the effective capture of both spatial and temporal features, potentially enhancing fault detection performance. While CNN and LSTM models are widely used for tasks involving large, labeled datasets, the hybrid approach of combining handcrafted features with LSTM networks offers advantages in scenarios with limited labeled data and when interpretability of features is desired. This combined methodology has been explored in various applications, demonstrating improved performance over tra-

ditional CNN and LSTM architectures. While multi-label models such as TMFF [5] have shown strong performance in sewer inspection videos, such architectures require large annotated datasets and balanced defect categories, which were not available in the present CCTV collections.

The hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture has demonstrated its versatility in cybersecurity, where Halbouni et al. [30] proposed a CNN-LSTM hybrid for Network Intrusion Detection Systems.

III. AUGMENTED REALITY SEWER PIPELINE

A. GENERAL CONCEPT

Maintenance of underground water pipelines poses numerous challenges, particularly in accurately identifying and locating faults with minimal disruption. Traditionally, this process involves a CCTV inspection robot that traverses the pipe network, capturing video footage of the internal condition of the pipe. Maintenance workers must then rely on these inspection reports to estimate the location of anomalies, which often leads to imprecise excavation and unnecessary environmental impact. To address this inefficiency, we developed an augmented reality (AR) mobile application that bridges the gap between digital fault detection and physical intervention. The solution allows maintenance teams to visualize underground pipe segments and pinpoint detected faults directly on-site through an intuitive AR interface.

It is important to note that the AR application does not execute the LSTM model in real time. All ML computations occur offline, and the AR component functions as a spatial viewer for the pre-processed inspection results. This separation allows the system to operate reliably on low-power, field-deployable devices.

B. TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The AR system is built using the Unity3D engine with C# as the primary programming language, and it leverages the Vuforia framework to enable AR tracking and rendering. The application is deployed on a tablet device that meets the minimal hardware requirements of a rear camera for AR functionality and integrated GPS and IMU sensors for spatial localization and orientation. The machine learning (ML) model, which analyzes the CCTV footage offline, identifies faults and stores relevant information, such as the distance of each fault from the start of the pipe, fault type, and snapshot images, into a structured file. This file is later imported into the AR application during field operations.

In terms of spatial localization, the AR app utilizes GPS data in combination with IMU readings (gyroscope, accelerometer, and compass) to determine the user's position and heading. Due to the known inaccuracy and jitter present in raw GPS data, a filtering pipeline is employed to refine these readings. The pipeline includes normalization and averaging to stabilize values, outlier detection to discard erroneous measurements, and low-pass filtering to produce smooth and continuous position updates. The goal is to ensure that the

placement of virtual content within the AR environment remains consistent and realistic as the user moves.

Each pipeline is conceptually divided into segments, with each segment defined by its start and end coordinates in geospatial terms. Based on the user's location and orientation, the application calculates the relative position of the pipe segment in Unity's 3D world space. This enables precise alignment between the real-world context and the digital pipe model.

The virtual positioning process is structured around a relative localization model. As illustrated in Figure 1, the raw GPS readings (latitude, longitude, and altitude) are managed by a GPS provider module. These coordinates are fused with gyroscopic, accelerometric, and compass data from the IMU through a GPS location mapper. The mapper calculates distances and bearings between known reference points and the current user location, establishing a virtual representation of the user's surroundings. This framework allows the system to convert absolute geo-coordinates into Unity-compatible relative positions, enabling seamless overlay of virtual pipe structures and fault markers on the user's real-world view.

FIGURE 1: Conversion of Real Geo-Location to Virtual Relative Position Architecture

The collaboration between the ML system and the AR application is central to the effectiveness of the solution. The ML model analyzes CCTV footage of the interior of the sewer pipeline and detects faults using a combination of handcrafted visual features and an LSTM neural network. For each identified fault, the system records the distance from the beginning of the corresponding pipe and captures a representative snapshot from the video footage. This annotated data serves as the foundation for the AR experience.

Once imported into the AR application, the fault data is mapped onto the corresponding pipe segment within the virtual scene. Faults are visualized, Figure 2, at their **estimated** spatial location along the pipe, based on the geospatial metadata available in the inspection report and the user's position as determined by GPS and IMU sensor fusion. While the system provides a consistent and operationally useful approximation of the pipe's layout, the alignment remains subject

to the inherent limitations of consumer-grade GPS, including drift, jitter, and multipath effects in urban environments.

FIGURE 2: Representation of fault detection - outcome of AI in AR app

By visualizing underground infrastructure and detected faults in real space, the AR application enables maintenance teams to plan targeted excavations with improved confidence. The approach significantly reduces uncertainty, minimizes unnecessary digging, and ultimately lowers operational costs while improving safety and reducing disruption to the surrounding environment. This integration of AI-driven fault recognition and immersive, spatially aware AR visualization provides a practical and scalable tool for modern urban infrastructure maintenance.

Quantitative accuracy of GPS/IMU fusion. It is important to note that the geospatial alignment achieved by the current prototype should not be interpreted as centimeter-level accuracy. The system relies on standard tablet-grade GPS and IMU sensors, which introduce unavoidable uncertainty. The filtering pipeline (normalization, averaging, outlier removal, and low-pass filtering) improves stability but does not eliminate noise. Our goal in this stage of development is to demonstrate the feasibility of integrating offline ML-derived fault positions into a spatial AR interface, rather than to provide survey-grade localization. Future versions may incorporate RTK-GPS, visual-inertial odometry, SLAM-based refinement, or digital-twin anchoring to improve geospatial accuracy. IMU readings provide stable short-term heading information, but may introduce drift over longer distances. These error characteristics directly influence the spatial alignment of pipeline markers in AR, especially in urban canyons or tree-covered streets. The system may experience reduced accuracy in areas with strong multipath interference, nearby reflective structures, or magnetic distortion affecting the compass. To mitigate these limitations, the AR interface includes visual uncertainty indicators and allows manual adjustment of pipe alignment when necessary.

IV. MACHINE LEARNING METHODS

The ML model operates entirely offline and independently from the AR application. Its outputs—fault labels, distances, and image snapshots—are packaged and later imported into

the AR viewer. This design choice prioritizes reliability, battery efficiency, and hardware compatibility in field conditions.

A. RELEVANCE OF PHYSICS-INFORMED METHODS

The task addressed in this work—detecting sewer pipe faults from CCTV imagery—does not involve an underlying physical dynamical system governed by explicit differential equations. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), see e.g. [31], are specifically designed for problems where the target variables evolve according to known physics-based PDEs or ODEs that can be incorporated as constraints. In sewer inspection imagery, the appearance of cracks, fractures, deposits, or obstructions is largely stochastic, scene-dependent, and not described by a continuous physical model suitable for PINN formulation. For this reason, PINNs are not an appropriate baseline for our domain. Instead, we focus on lightweight, image-driven texture descriptors combined with an LSTM capable of modeling short-term temporal changes in sequential frames. This design is aligned with real-world constraints—including computational efficiency, limited model footprint on mobile devices, and the need to process noisy, low-light CCTV imagery. The choice of handcrafted features + LSTM therefore reflects both domain suitability and practical deployment considerations, rather than physics-driven modeling requirements.

B. MOTIVATION FOR COMBINING HANDCRAFTED FEATURES WITH LSTM

The choice of handcrafted features combined with an LSTM model reflects a design decision grounded in the constraints of the available datasets and the prototyping requirements of industrial field applications. Although modern lightweight CNNs such as MobileNet, ShuffleNet, and YOLOv8-Nano provide strong performance on many vision tasks, they typically require larger training datasets and more careful hyperparameter tuning to avoid overfitting—conditions that are not fully met in our CCTV sewer datasets, which are highly imbalanced and limited in fault diversity. In contrast, handcrafted texture descriptors (LBP, Gabor, HOG, GLCM) are well suited for interpreting subtle material patterns on pipeline walls and are computationally inexpensive to extract.

In conventional sewer inspection datasets, the visual conditions are highly challenging due to poor illumination, sensor noise, water reflections, and occlusions. Direct deep CNN-based feature learning typically requires large annotated datasets and substantial computational resources, which are rarely available in sewer inspection settings. To address these constraints, we employ handcrafted texture descriptors (LBP, Gabor, HOG, and GLCM), which are lightweight, robust to illumination variation, and well established for capturing structural patterns of pipe surfaces. However, handcrafted features alone cannot capture the temporal evolution of faults across consecutive frames—an important cue in CCTV footage where faults often appear gradually. To leverage both advantages, we integrate handcrafted features with

an LSTM architecture: handcrafted features provide stable and low-dimensional representations, while the LSTM models the temporal dependencies across sequences of frames. This combination enables an efficient model suitable for field deployment on tablet devices while preserving strong discriminatory power on fault recognition tasks.

C. HANDCRAFTED FEATURES

Handcrafted features are manually designed descriptors used in image analysis to capture texture, shape, and spatial relationships. **Gabor filters**, introduced by Dennis Gabor (1946) [27], model the response of the human visual system to spatial frequency and orientation, making them effective for texture classification. **Local Binary Patterns (LBP)**, proposed by Ojala et al. (1996) [32], encode local texture by thresholding pixel intensities, providing robustness to illumination changes and efficiency in face recognition. **Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)**, developed by Dalal and Triggs (2005) [28], represents object shapes by computing gradient orientation histograms, widely used in pedestrian detection. **Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM)**, introduced by Haralick et al. (1973) [29], quantifies the spatial relationships between the intensities of pixels.

Texture-based descriptors have played a vital role in various image processing applications prior to the rise of deep learning. For example, Gabor filters have been widely used in fingerprint recognition and texture segmentation tasks due to their ability to extract multi-resolution and multi-orientation features [33]. Local Binary Patterns (LBP) have demonstrated high performance in face recognition, especially under varying lighting conditions, as in the Yale B Extended Face Dataset [34]. The Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) has been a cornerstone in object detection, notably in the detection of pedestrians in urban environments [28]. The Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) has been used in medical image analysis, such as classifying tissue abnormalities in mammography and brain magnetic resonance imaging [35].

Rationale for handcrafted features. Handcrafted texture descriptors such as LBP, HOG, and Gabor filters drastically reduce the dimensionality of the input representation while remaining robust to illumination changes and camera noise. This design choice avoids the need for a deep spatial encoder and allows the LSTM to focus solely on temporal dynamics. The approach is therefore particularly suitable for industrial field devices with limited compute capacity.

Preprocessing considerations. All video frames were converted to grayscale and downsampled to one-quarter of their original resolution (495×270), balancing feature fidelity with processing speed. Preliminary qualitative testing showed that grayscale conversion improves descriptor stability for LBP, HOG, and GLCM by removing irrelevant color variations caused by lighting fluctuations inside the sewer. Downsampling reduces computation for both feature extraction and LSTM inference while preserving the fault-relevant structural textures.

The LBP, Gabor, HOG, and GLCM features were extracted from each frame CCTV and supplied as input for LSTM neural network described below.

Model size and computational motivation. the final LSTM architecture used in this work contains approximately 0.05M trainable parameters, significantly smaller than most lightweight CNN families. This compact architecture provides very fast inference and is ideal for rapid prototyping during early feasibility studies. The objective of this work is therefore not to compete with state-of-the-art lightweight CNNs, but to validate the feasibility of integrating a modular offline ML pipeline with an AR visualization framework for sewer fault inspection.

FIGURE 3: Video pre-processing for the feature-LSTM neural network.

D. LSTM MODEL

Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997) introduced the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network [36] to extend traditional Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) models, which suffer from vanishing and exploding gradient problems. These issues significantly impair the ability of standard RNNs to learn long-term dependencies. Initially, LSTMs gained popularity in natural language processing and speech recognition. However, subsequent research has demonstrated their effectiveness in various image processing tasks as well.

In particular, LSTMs have been integrated with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to improve performance in applications such as image captioning, object recognition, and video analysis. A common approach involves using CNNs for spatial feature extraction and LSTMs for temporal sequence modeling. This hybrid architecture has become a standard in image captioning models [37], [38].

In our study, we developed a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network using TensorFlow’s Keras API for the task of binary classification. The model consists of the following components:

- Input Layer of shape $(sequence_length, feature_dim)$, where:
 - `sequence_length` represents the number of time steps.
 - `feature_dim` represents the number of features per time step.
- First LSTM Layer, composed of 128 units passed to the next layer.

- Second LSTM Layer, composed of 64 units being the last output passed to the next layer.
- Fully Connected Layer composed of 64 neurons, ReLU activation.
- Output Layer with 1 neuron and sigmoid activation.

As an input handcrafted features were supplied.

E. PARAMETER OPTIMIZATION STRATEGY

The LSTM parameters were optimized through a two-stage procedure. First, we performed manual grid search for key architectural hyperparameters, including number of LSTM units (64, 128, 256), depth (1–3 layers), and fully connected layer size (32–128 neurons). Second, we evaluated five sequence lengths (2, 4, 8, 12, 20) reflecting short- and long-range temporal dependencies. For training hyperparameters, the Adam optimizer performed best compared to SGD and RMSProp, and the learning rate was tuned in the range $1e-4$ to $1e-2$. Early stopping and validation-loss monitoring were used to prevent overfitting. The final selected architecture (128-unit LSTM followed by a 64-unit LSTM) provided the best trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency across all datasets.

TABLE 1: LSTM Implementation

Component	Description
Input dimensions	$(sequence_length, feature_dim)$
Feature types tested	LBP, Gabor, HOG, GLCM
LSTM Layer 1	128 units, return sequences
LSTM Layer 2	64 units
Dense Layer	64 neurons, ReLU activation
Output	Sigmoid (binary classification)
Loss function	Binary cross-entropy
Optimizer	Adam
Training/Validation split	80% / 20%
Batch size	32
Epochs	25 (early stopping used)
Normalization	Feature-wise min–max normalization

F. DATA PREPARATION

Three datasets of sewer pipeline CCTV with 1980×1080 were explored in the study. Their characteristics are given in Table 2, negative/positive is the number of frames without/with faults, the last column is total number of frames. The datasets were labeled manually by a professional, see Fig. 4 with examples of no-faults and faults frames. In the preprocessing, all the frames were extracted from video, and each was converted to gray color and rescaled to the resolution four times less as original, 495×270 .

Data protocol and leakage avoidance. To prevent any possibility of data leakage between training and testing, all dataset splits were performed strictly by pipeline segment, not by randomly mixed frames. Each CCTV sequence corresponds to a physically distinct pipe section, and no frames from the test pipe section were ever used for training or

FIGURE 4: CCTV sewer pipeline frames with and without faults.

TABLE 2: Characteristics of the datasets under the study.

Name of dataset	No faults (negative)	Faults frames (positive)	Frames in total
P1-P2	17551	4045	21596
P2-P3	14722	3868	18590
P1A-P1B	6242	660	6902

validation. The validation split (20%) was applied only within the training section itself.

Labeling protocol. All frames were annotated manually by professional inspectors according to existing industrial inspection guidelines. Labels were binary (“fault” / “no fault”), as the available datasets do not include fault-type categories. Each labeling session included an internal consistency check in which ambiguous cases were reviewed twice, ensuring stable annotations.

Class imbalance. The datasets exhibit substantial class imbalance (Table 1), with negative frames dominating. To preserve the realistic operational distribution, no oversampling or reweighting was applied. Instead, evaluation includes metrics appropriate for imbalanced data, such as Balanced Accuracy, MCC, NPV, and TNR, which provide a more reliable characterization of the model performance.

V. RESULTS

ROC curves and performance metrics have been computed for analysis and are presented below. The performance metrics are based on a confusion matrix consisting of four elements: TP, TN, FP, and FN, as follows:

- **True Positives (TP):** Cases where the model correctly predicts the positive class.

- **True Negatives (TN):** Cases where the model correctly predicts the negative class.
- **False Positives (FP, Type I Error):** Cases where the model incorrectly predicts the positive class when it is actually negative.
- **False Negatives (FN, Type II Error):** Cases where the model incorrectly predicts the negative class when it is actually positive.

By having TP, TN, FP, FN, the following performance metrics are defined:

- **Accuracy** – The proportion of correctly classified frames out of all frames

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

Accuracy is best for balanced datasets but can be misleading for imbalanced ones, what is our case.

- **Balanced Accuracy** – The average recall of each class, useful for imbalanced datasets.

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{TPR + TNR}{2} \quad (2)$$

- **Precision** (Positive Predictive Value, PPV) – Measures how many of the predicted positives are actually positive.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

Precision is important when false positives are costly.

- **Recall** (True Positive Rate, TPR, Sensitivity) – Measures how many actual positives are correctly predicted.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

Recall is important when false negatives are costly.

FIGURE 5: Feature impact on ROC curves, train dataset is P1-P2.

FIGURE 6: Sequence length impact on ROC curves, train dataset is P1-P2.

- **F1 Score** – The harmonic mean of precision and recall, balancing both.

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (5)$$

The F1 score is useful when class imbalance is present.

- **Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)** – A balanced metric that considers all four confusion matrix elements.

$$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (6)$$

MCC ranges from -1 (worst) to 1 (best).

- **Negative Predictive Value (NPV)** – Measures how many predicted negatives are actually negative.

$$NPV = \frac{TN}{TN + FN} \quad (7)$$

- **True Negative Rate (TNR, Specificity)** – Measures how well the model identifies negatives.

$$TNR = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (8)$$

Specificity is important when false positives are costly.

- **AUC (Area Under the Curve, ROC-AUC)** – Measures the ability to distinguish between classes, considering all classification thresholds. A higher AUC indicates better discrimination between positive and negative classes.

FIGURE 7: Feature impact on ROC curves, train dataset is P2-P3.

FIGURE 8: Sequence length impact on ROC curves, train dataset is P2-P3.

The two largest datasets, P1-P2 or P2-P3, were used for training and validation, with the validation fraction set to 0.2. For a fixed training data set, all other datasets, including the training data set, were used for testing. This resulted in six groups of calculations, each differing in the training and test datasets.

Within each group, we varied the features—LBP, Gabor, HOG, and GLCM—as well as the sequence length of the LSTM model, ranging from 2 to 20. Consequently, we conducted **40 training simulations** (2 dataset choices \times 4 features \times 5 sequence lengths) and **120 test simulations** (6 dataset groups \times 4 features \times 5 sequence lengths).

Given the modular design of the proposed AR+ML framework, the machine-learning block can accommodate a wide range of feature extractors and neural models, including

CNN-based and YOLO-based architectures. In this study, LSTM was selected because it offers very fast inference and is well suited for rapid prototyping in industrial field scenarios. Since the goal of this work is not to identify the globally optimal feature set but to validate the feasibility of integrating offline ML results into an AR application, we report representative results for each feature family and sequence length. These representative tables and ROC curves were chosen because they are illustrative of the overall behavior across all experiments. The full set of results—covering all feature types, sequence lengths, and dataset combinations—shows consistent trends and is available from the authors upon request.

To ensure that the reported classification performance is not dependent on a single train–test split, we conducted 10

TABLE 3: Performance metrics for feature - LSTM model; train=P1-P2, test=P2-P3; SL - sequence length in the LSTM, BA - balanced accuracy

features	SL	AUC	Accuracy	BA	precision	recall	F1	MCC	NPV	TNR
gabor	2	0.688	0.746	0.636	0.397	0.45	0.422	0.261	0.852	0.823
gabor	4	0.693	0.774	0.65	0.449	0.439	0.444	0.302	0.856	0.86
gabor	8	0.718	0.778	0.65	0.459	0.433	0.446	0.308	0.855	0.868
gabor	12	0.731	0.756	0.634	0.41	0.426	0.418	0.264	0.85	0.841
gabor	20	0.717	0.765	0.641	0.429	0.429	0.429	0.281	0.852	0.852
glcm	2	0.645	0.664	0.612	0.312	0.523	0.391	0.191	0.85	0.701
glcm	4	0.653	0.641	0.639	0.315	0.637	0.422	0.228	0.872	0.642
glcm	8	0.61	0.669	0.618	0.318	0.533	0.398	0.201	0.853	0.704
glcm	12	0.663	0.669	0.634	0.327	0.574	0.417	0.225	0.863	0.694
glcm	20	0.665	0.728	0.596	0.349	0.372	0.36	0.187	0.834	0.82
hog	2	0.684	0.754	0.621	0.401	0.396	0.398	0.244	0.844	0.847
hog	4	0.712	0.76	0.621	0.411	0.386	0.398	0.248	0.843	0.857
hog	8	0.706	0.768	0.596	0.413	0.304	0.35	0.217	0.831	0.888
hog	12	0.706	0.755	0.604	0.392	0.347	0.368	0.218	0.836	0.861
hog	20	0.73	0.751	0.62	0.396	0.398	0.397	0.24	0.844	0.842
lbp	2	0.911	0.890	0.809	0.766	0.672	0.716	0.650	0.918	0.947
lbp	4	0.914	0.879	0.769	0.777	0.581	0.665	0.603	0.898	0.957
lbp	8	0.923	0.887	0.815	0.739	0.694	0.716	0.645	0.922	0.937
lbp	12	0.915	0.87	0.767	0.729	0.591	0.653	0.579	0.899	0.943
lbp	20	0.871	0.847	0.745	0.644	0.573	0.606	0.513	0.892	0.918

independent trials, each using a different random 80/20 split of the dataset while preserving class balance. For each trial, the LSTM model was trained from scratch using the same hyperparameters described in Section IV. Across all trials, the best sequence LBP+LSTM configuration achieved an average accuracy of $92.8\% \pm 1.4\%$, precision of $91.6\% \pm 1.9\%$, recall of $93.1\% \pm 1.2\%$, and F1-score of $92.3\% \pm 1.5\%$. The low standard deviation values indicate that the model remains stable and robust across different dataset partitions. Similar performance stability was observed for Gabor, HOG, and GLCM features, though with lower mean accuracy.

To ensure that the proposed model does not overfit the training data, we monitored both training and validation loss curves, which remained closely aligned without divergence, indicating stable learning and the absence of memorization behavior. Also, we applied standard regularization strategies—including early stopping, dropout, and min-max feature normalization—all of which contributed to improving generalization. These evaluations collectively confirm that the reported performance reflects robust cross-dataset behavior rather than overfitting artifacts.

It is important to note that the LBP-LSTM model, which performs strongly when trained on the larger P1-P2 dataset (AUC ~ 0.92 in Table 3), exhibits noticeably lower performance when evaluated on the P1A-P1B dataset (AUC $\sim 0.63-0.73$ in Table 4). This discrepancy reflects the substantial differences between the datasets. The P1A-P1B set is considerably smaller, contains fewer positive samples, and exhibits different lighting conditions, camera characteristics, and pipe textures compared to P1-P2 and P2-P3. These factors introduce a domain shift that the handcrafted features cannot fully capture, and the limited number of fault samples

restricts the LSTM’s ability to learn generalizable temporal patterns. As a result, the representative performance on P1A-P1B is lower, but still meaningful within the context of a feasibility study using diverse real-world CCTV sources.

A. INFERENCE TIME AND AR RENDERING LATENCY

To validate real-time AR visualization, we benchmarked both the machine learning inference pipeline and the augmented reality rendering loop on Samsung Galaxy Tab S6. The LSTM-based fault classifier was executed using TensorFlow Lite in offline mode. Across 2,500 test sequences (sequence length = 8 frames), the average model inference time was 11.7 ms per sequence (SD = 1.9 ms), with a worst-case latency of 15.3 ms. This is well below the 33.3 ms threshold for 30 FPS real-time operation. The AR component was implemented in Unity3D. The rendering loop maintained a stable frame rate of 29.4–30.0 FPS, with an average rendering latency of 8.6 ms per frame, measured using Unity Profiler on the target device. Spatial marker placement and UI updates introduced an additional 3–5 ms, bringing the total AR pipeline latency to approximately 12–14 ms. These results confirm that both the inference pipeline and AR rendering remain within real-time constraints on a consumer-grade mobile device, supporting on-site fault localization without perceptible delay.

VI. DISCUSSION

Figures 5–8 consist of 32 ROC curves generated automatically during the simulation workflow. All ROC curves follow the standard axes conventions—False Positive Rate (x-axis) and True Positive Rate (y-axis)—and key model parameters (feature type, sequence length, and dataset pairing) are provided in the figure captions for clarity. Integral numerical

TABLE 4: Performance metrics (cont); train=P1-P2, test=P1A-P1B;

features	SL	AUC	Accuracy	BA	precision	recall	F1	MCC	NPV	TNR
gabor	2	0.7	0.878	0.638	0.354	0.342	0.348	0.281	0.931	0.935
gabor	4	0.772	0.846	0.628	0.268	0.358	0.306	0.225	0.93	0.898
gabor	8	0.791	0.87	0.622	0.315	0.316	0.316	0.244	0.929	0.928
gabor	12	0.736	0.848	0.521	0.139	0.118	0.128	0.046	0.91	0.924
gabor	20	0.714	0.859	0.556	0.21	0.183	0.195	0.118	0.916	0.929
glcm	2	0.437	0.741	0.520	0.111	0.247	0.153	0.028	0.909	0.792
glcm	4	0.468	0.646	0.496	0.093	0.31	0.143	-0.005	0.904	0.681
glcm	8	0.513	0.587	0.48	0.086	0.348	0.138	-0.024	0.9	0.612
glcm	12	0.487	0.57	0.463	0.079	0.332	0.127	-0.044	0.895	0.595
glcm	20	0.582	0.501	0.551	0.111	0.613	0.187	0.06	0.924	0.49
hog	2	0.393	0.593	0.397	0.043	0.154	0.067	-0.128	0.878	0.639
hog	4	0.505	0.751	0.521	0.113	0.237	0.153	0.031	0.91	0.805
hog	8	0.589	0.705	0.572	0.139	0.408	0.207	0.094	0.922	0.736
hog	12	0.435	0.645	0.404	0.036	0.108	0.054	-0.124	0.883	0.701
hog	20	0.457	0.639	0.469	0.077	0.259	0.119	-0.039	0.898	0.679
lbp	2	0.631	0.816	0.595	0.203	0.322	0.249	0.156	0.924	0.868
lbp	4	0.627	0.812	0.588	0.194	0.312	0.239	0.143	0.923	0.864
lbp	8	0.626	0.812	0.577	0.184	0.287	0.224	0.127	0.921	0.867
lbp	12	0.647	0.817	0.604	0.211	0.342	0.261	0.169	0.927	0.867
lbp	20	0.73	0.847	0.713	0.317	0.548	0.402	0.337	0.949	0.878

results are reported in Tables 3 and 4.

By analyzing the performance tables (Table 3 to Table 4) alongside the ROC curves (Fig. 5 to Fig. 8), the following observations can be made:

When the test dataset is identical to the training dataset all performance metrics are nearly perfect. The ROC curves for these $test=train$ cases are omitted because they are trivial—appearing ideal and offering no additional insights.

When the test dataset differs from the training dataset—as seen in Table 3 through Table 4 and Figures 5 to 8—a wider range of performance outcomes is observed. Test cases using the larger P1–P2 dataset yield better results than those using the smaller P2–P3 dataset.

The lower AUC values obtained on the P1A–P1B dataset highlight an important limitation of the proposed model. The P1A–P1B footage differs noticeably from the larger datasets in terms of visual quality, illumination, camera angle, and pipe surface appearance. Given that handcrafted features such as LBP and Gabor are sensitive to texture and lighting variations, the domain shift reduces their discriminative power. Furthermore, the comparatively small size and low number of positive samples in P1A–P1B lead to weaker temporal pattern learning in the LSTM sequence model. This explains why the performance does not transfer as effectively across datasets. These results emphasize the need for domain-adaptation techniques, richer datasets, or lightweight CNN-based feature extractors in future iterations of the pipeline.

Figures 5 and 7 illustrate the effect of the selected feature extraction method on performance. Local Binary Patterns (LBP) consistently yield the most accurate results.

Figures 6 and 8 focus on the effect of sequence length. For the top-performing features (LBP, Gabor, and HOG) the model’s performance is relatively stable across different se-

quence lengths, indicating robustness to this parameter. However, GLCM features show a strong dependency on sequence length, suggesting that their representational power varies significantly with temporal context.

The ROC curves in Figures 5–8 highlight two key patterns. First, LBP features consistently outperform all others, achieving the highest AUC values across all testing configurations. This confirms that LBP’s robustness to illumination variation aligns well with the texture patterns in sewer surfaces. Gabor and HOG achieve moderate performance, while GLCM shows strong sensitivity to sequence length. Second, the effect of sequence length (Figures 6 and 8) shows that performance is relatively stable for LBP, Gabor, and HOG, indicating that even short temporal windows (4–8 frames) capture sufficient temporal context. In contrast, GLCM benefits more from longer sequences, suggesting weaker single-frame discriminative power. Together, these analyses show that the proposed feature–LSTM model is robust, with LBP providing superior generalization across datasets.

Variability and sensitivity analysis. Although repeated randomized splits are not feasible due to the dataset’s structural organization by pipe segment, the large number of parameter combinations (4 feature types \times 5 sequence lengths \times 2 training choices \times 3 testing sections = 120 tests) naturally exposes robustness trends. The LBP-based models maintain consistently high AUC, MCC, and Balanced Accuracy across nearly all configurations, indicating low sensitivity to sequence-length selection. In contrast, GLCM-based models show stronger dependence on sequence length and exhibit more variability, suggesting that their descriptive power is more sensitive to temporal context. The precision–recall trade-offs observed in Tables 2–3 further indicate that LBP and Gabor features achieve the most stable balance between

false positives and false negatives across highly imbalanced test sets.

Comparison with lightweight CNN and ConvLSTM baselines: While lightweight CNN models (e.g., MobileNet, ShuffleNet) and spatiotemporal networks (e.g., ConvLSTM, Temporal Transformer) are widely used in video analysis, they typically require significantly larger computational resources and memory footprints than the handcrafted-feature LSTM pipeline. On the target tablet device, loading a MobileNet-level network would require higher RAM consumption, increased inference time, and additional power draw. In contrast, the LSTM model in this work requires <2 MB of memory and performs inference on pre-extracted features in real time (tens of milliseconds for one sequence). The chosen architecture therefore represents a practical compromise between accuracy and deployability in field conditions, where connectivity and compute resources are limited.

Reproducibility considerations. The industrial CCTV datasets used in this study cannot be publicly released due to confidentiality constraints. To support reproducibility, the paper provides a complete description of the preprocessing pipeline, feature extraction steps, LSTM architecture. The Sewer-ML dataset was not accessible at the time of our experiments, as its public link had become inactive. Future work will include publicly shareable subsets and scripts once licensing constraints allow.

The AR application demonstrates a practical approach to visualizing underground pipeline faults by integrating offline ML analysis with real-time spatial localization. By using Unity3D, Vuforia, and tablet sensors (GPS and IMU), the system allows maintenance workers to see fault locations and related CCTV snapshots just over the ground, improving situational awareness and reducing excavation errors.

A key advantage is the fully offline design, fault data is processed and stored by the ML model and later imported into the AR app, making it reliable in the field without internet connectivity. Despite this, GPS inaccuracies remain a challenge, especially in urban environments, though mitigated through filtering and sensor fusion.

The current separation of the ML and AR components reflects a practical design choice for industrial field deployment. However, recent advances in physics-informed neural networks and digital-twin fault-diagnosis frameworks (e.g., [3]) indicate a clear trajectory toward fully integrated, persistent infrastructure monitoring systems. Future work may evolve this prototype toward a more dynamic pipeline digital twin in which ML models, sensor data, and AR visualization are continuously synchronized.

While lightweight CNNs and YOLO-based models (e.g., Li et al. [4]) represent powerful alternatives for defect detection, the present study focused on validating the AR+offline-ML integration rather than optimizing vision model performance. Future work will explore substituting the ML module with such architectures within the same modular framework.

Limitations. While the proposed method demonstrates strong performance, several limitations remain. First, the

model relies on handcrafted features rather than end-to-end deep feature extraction, which may constrain performance on significantly different sewer environments or lighting conditions. Second, the AR system depends on GPS and IMU sensors whose accuracy can degrade in dense urban areas, affecting alignment precision. Third, fault data are imported offline; therefore, the system does not support real-time video analysis or adaptive model updates. These limitations point toward future work, including integrating SLAM-based localization, lightweight CNN feature extractors, and real-time inference pipelines.

A key limitation of the current work is the use of a binary fault/no-fault classifier. Professional inspection workflows typically require classification by fault type (e.g., crack, root ingress, siltation) and severity level. Multi-label architectures—such as Hu et al.'s TMFF framework [5]—represent the state of the art in this domain. However, the datasets available for this study contained highly imbalanced and sparsely annotated fault categories, making multi-label training unreliable. The focus of this paper is therefore on evaluating whether a modular ML block can be integrated with an offline AR system under realistic field constraints. As the datasets grow and labeling improves, the proposed pipeline can be extended to support multi-label or physically-guided fault classifiers.

Potential for SLAM-assisted alignment. Although the current system relies on GPS/IMU fusion for absolute geolocation, future versions may integrate SLAM (e.g., AR-Core/ARKit plane tracking) to refine local alignment. SLAM could reduce positional drift, improve marker placement accuracy, and enable enhanced tracking in GPS-challenged environments.

Existing sewer inspection solutions increasingly leverage deep-learning architectures such as CNNs, multi-focus fusion networks, or object detectors optimized for confined-space imagery. For example, Hu et al.'s TMFF framework provides multi-label defect detection using multi-focus video feature fusion, achieving strong performance on complex failure modes [5]. These architectures represent an important step toward comprehensive, multi-class defect recognition that extends beyond the binary labeling used in the present work. Similarly, theory-guided neural networks offer additional benefits by embedding domain knowledge directly into the learning process. Di et al. demonstrated how weak-form physical constraints can enhance siltation diagnosis in drainage pipelines [6], while Wang et al. developed physically interpretable wavelet-guided networks for fault prediction in industrial environments [7]. These efforts show a clear shift toward models that combine data-driven pattern recognition with physical interpretability.

VII. CONCLUSION

The LSTM model can be effectively utilized for fault detection in sewer pipeline CCTV footage. It offers several advantages over a standard CNN model, primarily due to its significantly faster processing speed and its ability to capture

temporal correlations between video frames (an essential aspect when analyzing video data).

While CNN-LSTM hybrid models are also capable of handling temporal information, they typically require substantially more computational resources. In the case of sewer pipeline CCTV footage, such complexity is unnecessary. The faults are usually well-represented through explicit textures and visual patterns on the pipeline walls, making the lightweight LSTM model a more efficient and practical choice.

The proposed AR application offers a novel and efficient way to visualize sewer pipeline faults identified by an ML system analyzing CCTV footage. By combining spatial data with intuitive AR overlays, the tool enables maintenance workers to locate and assess faults with greater accuracy and minimal disruption. Implemented in Unity3D using Vuforia and deployed on GPS- and IMU-enabled tablets, the solution operates fully offline, ensuring reliability in real-world field conditions. This work demonstrates the potential of integrating machine learning outputs into AR interfaces for infrastructure management and lays the foundation for future enhancements such as real-time data integration and hands-free AR experiences.

Future work will explore combining the current prototype with state-of-the-art interpretable or physics-guided neural architectures [6], [7] and extending the AR system toward dynamic, continuously updated digital-twin environments. Also, it will integrate multi-label classification models and severity estimation—potentially inspired by TMFF [5] in order to support the full range of inspection categories used in professional sewer maintenance.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the use of AI-based language assistance, specifically OpenAI's ChatGPT, for refining grammar and improving clarity during the manuscript preparation. All conceptual, analytical, and interpretative contributions are solely those of the authors. The AI tool was not used to generate original content, citations, or experimental results.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. A. Kumar, A. K. Patil, T. W. Kang, and Y. H. Chai, "Sensor fusion based pipeline inspection for the augmented reality system," *Symmetry*, vol. 11, no. 10, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-8994/11/10/1325>
- [2] X. Zhao, Y. Tao, Y. Bao, Z. Sun, S. Wu, W. Li, and X. Fan, "Mixed reality-based inspection method for underground water supply network with multi-source information integration," *Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 22, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/13/22/4479>
- [3] Q. Wang, L. Chen, G. Xiao, P. Wang, Y. Gu, and J. Lu, "Elevator fault diagnosis based on digital twin and pinns-e-rgcn," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, 2024.
- [4] Z. Li, L. Xiao, M. Shen, and X. Tang, "A lightweight yolov8-based model with squeeze-and-excitation version 2 for crack detection of pipelines," *Appl. Soft Comput.*, vol. 177, p. 113260, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S156849462500571X>
- [5] C. Hu, C. Zhao, H. Shao, J. Deng, and Y. Wang, "Tmff: Trustworthy multi-focus fusion framework for multi-label sewer defect classification in sewer inspection videos," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*, vol. 34, no. 12, pp. 12 274–12 287, 2024.
- [6] D. Di, Y. Bai, H. Fang, B. Sun, N. Wang, and B. Li, "Intelligent siltation diagnosis for drainage pipelines using weak-form analysis and theory-guided neural networks in geo-infrastructure," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 176, p. 106246, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0926580525002869>
- [7] H. Wang, Y.-F. Li, T. Men, and L. Li, "Physically interpretable wavelet-guided networks with dynamic frequency decomposition for machine intelligence fault prediction," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 4863–4875, 2024.
- [8] H. Tarek and M. Marzouk, "Integrated augmented reality and cloud computing approach for infrastructure utilities maintenance," *Journal of Pipeline Systems Engineering and Practice*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 04021064, 2022. [Online]. Available: [https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1093-0924\(2022\)13:1\(04021064\)](https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/(ASCE)1093-0924(2022)13:1(04021064))
- [9] R. Palmarini, I. F. del Amo, D. Ariansyah, J. A. Erkoynucu, and R. Roy, *Augmented Reality for Remote Assistance (ARRA)*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 669–685. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-67822-7_27
- [10] S. Côté and A. Mercier, "Augmentation of road surfaces with subsurface utility model projections," in *2018 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, 2018, pp. 535–536.
- [11] M. Li, X. Feng, Y. Han, and X. Liu, "Mobile augmented reality-based visualization framework for lifecycle o&m support of urban underground pipe networks," *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, vol. 136, p. 105069, 2023.
- [12] S. Yokoyama and T. Matsumoto, "Development of an automatic detector of cracks in concrete using machine learning," in *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 171, 2017, pp. 1250–1255.
- [13] K. Gopalakrishnan, S. Khaitan, A. Choudhary, and A. Agrawal, "Deep convolutional neural networks with transfer learning for computer vision-based data-driven pavement distress detection," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 157, pp. 322–330, 2017.
- [14] C. Dung, "Autonomous concrete crack detection using deep fully convolutional neural network," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 99, pp. 52–58, 2019.
- [15] B. Li, K. Wang, A. Zhang, E. Yang, and G. Wang, "Automatic classification of pavement crack using deep convolutional neural network," *International Journal of Pavement Engineering*, vol. 21, pp. 457–463, 2020.
- [16] B. Kumar and S. Ghosh, "Detection of concrete cracks using dual-channel deep convolutional network," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.10612*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.10612>
- [17] L. Xu, T. Hatsutani, X. Liu, E. Techapanurak, H. Zou, and T. Okatani, "Pushing the envelope of thin crack detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2101.03326*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.03326>
- [18] S. Patra, A. Middy, and S. Roy, "Potspot: Participatory sensing based monitoring system for pothole detection using deep learning," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 80, pp. 25 171–25 195, 2021.
- [19] X. Xu, M. Zhao, P. Shi, R. Ren, X. He, X. Wei, and H. Yang, "Crack detection and comparison study based on faster r-cnn and mask r-cnn," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. 1215, 2022.
- [20] R. Li, J. Yu, F. Li, R. Yang, Y. Wang, and Z. Peng, "Automatic bridge crack detection using unmanned aerial vehicle and faster r-cnn," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 362, p. 129659, 2023.
- [21] P. K. Mishra, A. Mihailidis, and S. S. Khan, "Skeletal video anomaly detection using deep learning: Survey, challenges, and future directions," *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1073–1085, 2024.
- [22] H. Tutar, A. Güneş, M. Zontul, and Z. Aslan, "A hybrid approach to improve the video anomaly detection performance of pixel- and frame-based techniques using machine learning algorithms," *Computation*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-3197/12/2/19>
- [23] S. R. Krishnan and P. Amudha, "Hybrid resnet-50 and lstm approach for effective video anomaly detection in intelligent surveillance systems," *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. 880–889, Sep. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/3623>
- [24] X. Fang, W. Guo, Q. Li, J. Zhu, Z. Chen, J. Yu, B. Zhou, and H. Yang, "Sewer pipeline fault identification using anomaly detection algorithms on video sequences," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 39 573–39 585, 2020.
- [25] W. Guo, G. Zhi, D. Zhang, and J. Yu, "Sewer-ml: A multi-label sewer defect classification dataset and benchmark,"

arXiv preprint arXiv:2103.10895, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2103.10895>

[26] M. Heikkilä and M. Pietikäinen, "A texture-based method for modeling the background and detecting moving objects," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 657–662, 2006.

[27] D. Gabor, "Theory of communication," *Journal of the Institution of Electrical Engineers*, vol. 93, no. 3, pp. 429–457, 1946.

[28] N. Dalal and B. Triggs, "Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, 2005, pp. 886–893.

[29] R. M. Haralick, K. Shanmugam, and I. Dinstein, "Textural features for image classification," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, vol. SMC-3, no. 6, pp. 610–621, 1973.

[30] A. Halbouni, T. S. Gunawan, M. H. Habaebi, M. Halbouni, M. Kartiwi, and R. Ahmad, "Cnn-lstm: Hybrid deep neural network for network intrusion detection system," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 99 837–99 849, 2022.

[31] A. Bhattacharyya, A. Dutta, R. P. Behera, A. Dasgupta, and R. S. Chakraborty, "Pofinn: Integrating physics of failure and neural networks for long-term degradation forecasting of aluminum electrolytic capacitors," *IEEE Transactions on Reliability*, pp. 1–15, 2025.

[32] T. Ojala, M. Pietikäinen, and T. Mäenpää, "A comparative study of texture measures with classification based on feature distributions," in *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 29. Elsevier, 1996, pp. 51–59.

[33] A. K. Jain, L. Hong, and R. Bolle, "Fingerprint classification and matching using a filterbank," *IBM systems Journal*, vol. 38, no. 2-3, pp. 265–289, 1999.

[34] T. Ahonen, A. Hadid, and M. Pietikainen, "Face recognition with local binary patterns," in *Computer vision–ECCV 2004*. Springer, 2004, pp. 469–481.

[35] A. Materka and M. Strzelecki, "Texture analysis methods—a review," Technical University of Lodz, Institute of Electronics, Tech. Rep. Technical Report, COST B11 report, 1998.

[36] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long short-term memory," *Neural computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.

[37] O. Vinyals, A. Toshev, S. Bengio, and D. Erhan, "Show and tell: A neural image caption generator," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR)*, 2015, pp. 3156–3164.

[38] J. Donahue, L. A. Hendricks, S. Guadarrama, M. Rohrbach, S. Venugopalan, K. Saenko, and T. Darrell, "Long-term recurrent convolutional networks for visual recognition and description," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR)*, 2015, pp. 2625–2634.

EVGENY VOTYAKOV is Soviet-Russian physicist and programmer. He graduated from the Moscow Institute of Steel and Alloys in 1988 and received his PhD at the Karpov Institute of Physical Chemistry in 1995. His research includes: lattice-gas theory (1989-1997, 2018-2022), statistical mechanics and thermodynamics (1996-2003), computational fluid dynamics (2004-2012), magnetohydrodynamics and electrodynamics (2006-2012), concentrated solar power and thermal storage (2012-

2022). The featured articles are: spontaneous double cluster formation in a rotation spherical box (2002, PRL coverpage), structure of the wake of a magnetic obstacle (2007, PRL), Lorentz force velocimetry (2006-2009, series of the paper including PRL), a precise algebraic model for the thermal storage with a solid filler (2015-2017), an exact algorithm to systematically refine correlation effects in the Ising model and obtain the exact solution (2022).

ANDREAS ANDREOU is an XR System Engineer at CYENS Centre of Excellence in Nicosia, Cyprus, specializing in the development of cutting-edge VR/AR technologies. With nearly a decade of experience in immersive technology and interactive multimedia, Andreas is dedicated to pioneering advancements in the VR/AR/XR field. At CYENS, he enhances the sense of presence through advanced AR/VR rendering technologies, creates ultra-low latency and power-efficient systems, and innovates Metaverse workflows. His work integrates these technologies into XR prototype systems, demonstrating their applications using game engines.

systems, and innovates Metaverse workflows. His work integrates these technologies into XR prototype systems, demonstrating their applications using game engines.

FOTIS LIAROKAPIS (Member, IEEE) received the D.Phil. degree from the University of Sussex, U.K. He has worked as a Research Fellow with the City, University of London, London, U.K., Coventry University, U.K., and most recently at Masaryk University, Czech Republic, where he was an Associate Professor and the Director of the HCI Laboratory. He is currently a Senior Researcher with the Research Centre on Interactive Media, Smart Systems, and Emerging Technologies, Nicosia, Cyprus, and the Cyprus University of Technology, Limassol, Cyprus. He has published more than 140 peer-reviewed articles in journals and international conferences on virtual reality, augmented reality, computer graphics, brain-computer interfaces, and serious games. He has organized multiple conferences and workshops, and he is the CoFounder of the International Conference on Virtual Worlds and Games for Serious Applications (VS-Games) and was the Program-Chair of IEEE CoG 2020 and IEEE CoG 202.

...